

ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF KASHKADARYA CHILDREN'S SUBJECT DANCES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the types, history and modern success of Kashkadarya children's dance art. Also, the styles of children's dances and movements in the region will be discussed

The national values, unique traditions and customs created in the most ancient times and enriched and polished by each new generation over the centuries are the fruit of the artistic thinking of our people, the most priceless spiritual treasure of the nation. The decision was an important event in the spiritual and social life of our country. Special attention was paid to the issue of "improving musical knowledge and skills of pupils and students, forming love for national culture in their hearts, identifying and supporting young talents¹." Children's folklore dances are also one of the main sources of formation of our national spirituality. After all, "a characteristic aspect of children's education in the primitive system was to introduce them to the customs, traditions, history of the clan, as well as folklore: narratives, songs and dances. In the primitive society, the holiday - religious ceremonies, which are called to join the youth in the big ranks, are widespread. These are unique games and competitions, the content of which is made up of labor activities, tribal customs, folk art. Dances were also performed in ceremonies, in which primitive people expressed their lives and failures, joys and sorrows²."

It is known that Uzbek folk dance has 3 school directions in a number of sources. In the years of independence, the focus on dance science increased, as a result of the research on the history of dance, it is now recognized that there are 5 dance schools³.

"Our compatriots know very well that 5 different schools of Uzbek national dance art have been formed. These are Ferghana-Tashkent, Khorezm, Bukhara-Samarkand, Karakalpak,

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to further develop the sphere of culture and art". "New Uzbekistan" newspaper, February 4, 2022, issue 25.

²Karaboev U. Holidays of Uzbekistan. T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 1991. -B.10.

³Madieva R. Dance has the soul of the nation. / "New Uzbekistan" newspaper, 2020 // <https://yuz.uz/authors>

Kashkadarya-Surkhandarya dance schools. These schools differ from each other in their uniqueness, attractiveness, elements, and local color of their actions⁴."

Five dance schools are indicated in the "Updated National List of Intangible Cultural Heritage Objects of Uzbekistan" presented by the Republican Scientific and Methodological Center of Folk Art and Cultural and Educational Affairs, as well as on the official website of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In our opinion, the reason for such a difference is explained by the fact that, as a result of a long-term historical process, communication opportunities were previously limited, the inhabitants of each region were distinguished by their lifestyle, work, and profession, and these characteristics were also reflected in their art and culture. The dances of these schools differ from each other not only in their music, style, and movements, but also in their costumes, jewelry, and decorations.

In particular, children's folklore works are mainly formed in the oral tradition and spread widely. It was sharpened in the wake of history, and later it acquired colorful genres and has reached our time.

The legendary Bactria and ancient Nasaf on the Great Silk Road have long attracted travelers from all over the world with their unique historical monuments, customs and traditions. The foundations of the Third Renaissance will be strengthened by teaching the younger generation the cultural and national wealth inherited from our great ancestors, and by continuing the historical traditions. The internal and external tourism opportunities of the regions will expand further. Boysun, Sherabad, Denov, Shahrisabz, Kitab, Chirokchi, Kamashi districts rely on ancient traditions in children's folk dances, and new decorations are combined with historical scenes with the help of unique decoration, color and image through modern design.

⁴ Introduction. Heritage Dance Masterpieces. Collection. (Study manual. Compilers: Kh. Hamidova, D. Sayfullaeva, S. Zokirova). T.: "Cholpon" publishing house, 2003. -B.3.

Children's folk songs of Kashkadarya play an important role in the series of artistic values that serve to improve the outlook of the young generation and enrich their spiritual world. They glorify noble ideas such as high patriotism, protection of the family and motherland, sanctity of the fatherland, glorification of the unity of the country. At the same time, their role and importance in introducing the most beautiful and noble values of our people to the whole world is incomparable. In the opinion of the famous ethnographer, professor I.Jabbarov, children's "moral maturity, strengthening of mutual friendly and fraternal relations, instilling feelings of respect and love for parents and adults, raising small children according to older children, and other issues of courtesy and respect Being controlled by the neighborhood or village community is one of the most wonderful traditions of the Uzbek people. In particular, the plots of ritual songs and dances, their important direction, subject dances, attract attention with their unique epic interpretations. Their genre affiliation, variants, composition of ideas and series of images in the plot system, and the scope of their distribution in oasis districts will be a source of special research.

In particular, activities in dance classes and clubs are characterized by their artistry, fun

and more creative pleasure, emotional feelings and figurative experiences for students. Today, even in dance education, more and more serious research is being carried out in order to organize classes on the basis of modern innovative pedagogical technologies, to improve traditional methods and to find new modern innovative ideas.

Folkloric songs and dances serve to inculcate patriotism, national and universal values, educational moral principles into the minds of children. The lyrics pay particular attention to the refrain. After all, "In some folk songs and chants, the chorus repeats the main melody in its entirety, and it is separated from the verses due to the repetitive text of the poem⁵." Due to the repetition of the refrain, words and actions are remembered by the child faster. In the mountainous villages of Boysun, Sariosiyo, Shahrisabz, Kitab districts, before the arrival of spring, the flowers bloom. The text of the children's song and dance "Boychechak" often repeats:

*"A little snowdrop that emerged from the hard ground,
A little snowdrop that rolled out of the soft ground -"*

lines are repeated over and over again during dance movements.

In the districts of Shurchi, Uzun, Karshi, Koson, attention is being paid to restoring the forgotten traditions of children's folk dances, to the widespread use of modern tools that directly affect the audience in stage composition interpretations. National and universal values are glorified in them. In the "Beshkarsak" dance, performed by teenage boys in the mountain villages of Boysun and Dehkanabad districts, all actions are performed under the rhythm of clapping and to the accompaniment of "oh-ho", "ho-ho" sounds.

"Beshkarsak", "Sandiqcha", "Chanqovuz", "Urchuq", "Carpet weaving", "Savachop", "Kuvi", "Sibizga", "Beshik", "Dombira", "Dupala-dup" in Surkhandarya-Kashkadarya regions. Children's folk dances such as "Yorghichak", "Rumolcha", "Boychechak", "Feast of Sumalak" are extremely popular. In them, the spirit of the oasis people, spiritual values, the inner world of children, their interests, dreams and desires found their mature and complete artistic expression. In particular, in the expression of dance movements, a wide place is given to songs-sayings that are limited to different situations or seasons and have a free theme.

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⁵National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. 6-j. Tashkent.: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2003. P.292.